
Data-Driven Bayesian Modeling for Type 2 Diabetes Risk Assessment and Personalized Recommendations Using R Shiny

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Making early risk predictions for Type 2 Diabetes, a prevalent and growing health issue in Sri Lanka, is essential for timely intervention. Existing machine learning and logistic regression approaches primarily provide point estimates, leaving a critical gap in capturing predictive uncertainty necessary for reliable clinical decision-making. To address this challenge, this study aims to develop a Bayesian logistic regression-based application for diabetes risk assessment using R. To quantify uncertainty and improve long-term patient outcomes, the system provides real-time visualizations and personalized recommendations. The Bayesian model, implemented with the *brms* package in R, extends standard logistic regression by incorporating multiple health indicators, including age, BMI, number of pregnancies, Diabetes Pedigree Function, glucose, blood pressure, skin thickness, and insulin within a probabilistic framework. Model training was conducted using the Pima Diabetes dataset from Kaggle, which contains no missing values. The system has been deployed as an interactive Shiny web application, allowing patients and clinicians to input health data and receive personalized risk probabilities along with tailored recommendations. When certain variables are missing (e.g., Diabetes Pedigree Function), the application can either calculate them using additional formulas or fit a simpler model with the available predictors. This flexibility enables users to evaluate the model under different input scenarios while obtaining useful predictions. The Bayesian logistic regression model achieved accuracy comparable to the benchmark GLM (0.783) while showing modest improvements in AUC (0.840), Brier score (0.153), and log loss (0.470), indicating superior probability calibration and supporting its suitability for clinical decision support. Overall, this study demonstrates that a probabilistic, uncertainty-aware modeling approach, implemented as an accessible Shiny web application, can enhance diabetes risk assessment and provide actionable, personalized insights for patients and clinicians.

Keywords: *Bayesian Logistic Regression, brms Package, Diabetes Pedigree Function, Predictive Uncertainty*

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